

Analysis of Jack London's works

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Annotatsiya : Mazkur maqolada mashhur ingliz adabiyoti vakillaridan biri bo'lgan Jek Londonning (Jack London) hayot yo'li haqisa qisqacha to'xlab o'tiladi va uning eng mashhur asarlari ,ulardagi qahramonlar taqdiri tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: harakter, hayvonlar, romannavist, mag'lubiyat .

Abstract:In this article, the life path of Jack London, one of the representatives of the famous English literature, will be briefly discussed and his most famous works and the fate of the characters in them will be analyzed.

Key words: character, animals, novelist, failure

John Griffith Chaney(January 12, 1876 – November 22, 1916), higher recognised as Jack London, became an American novelist, journalist and activist. A pioneer of industrial fiction and American magazines, he turned into one of the first American authors to grow to be an global superstar and earn a massive fortune from writing. He turned into additionally an innovator withinside the style that might later emerge as recognized as technology fiction. London turned into a part of the unconventional literary group "The Crowd" in San Francisco and a passionate recommend of animal rights, workers' rights and socialism. London wrote numerous works handling those

topics, including his dystopian novel *The Iron Heel*, his non-fiction exposé *The People of the Abyss*, *War of the Classes*, and *Before Adam*.

London's profession as a novelist started rapidly after the flip of the 20th century with the booklet of *A Daughter of the Snows*. It ended nineteen novels later with the posthumous book of *The Assassination Bureau, Ltd.* in 1963. The novels range broadly in length, issue matter, and (especially) creative quality, for whilst London ought to write bold, violent, Analysis • Jack London's reputation as a creator occurred in large part thru his capability to realistically interpret humanity's battle in an adverse surroundings. Early in his profession, London found out that he had no expertise for invention, that during his writing he could need to be an interpreter of the matters that are, in preference to an author of the matters that could be. Accordingly, he drew his plots, characters, themes, and settings from real-lifestyles reviews and posted accounts. London's profession as a novelist commenced rapidly after the flip of the 20th century with the book of *A Daughter of the Snows*. It ended nineteen novels later with the posthumous guide of *The Assassination Bureau, Ltd.* in 1963. The novels range extensively in length, problem matter, and (especially) creative quality, for at the same time as London should write bold, violent, and from time to time primitive quick memories of large energy, depicting the frontier surroundings and the human conflict inside it in memorable fashion, his novels frequently suffered from weak point of shape and immoderate didacticism. London's failure of invention, in no way a huge hassle in his brief tales, all too frequently surfaced in his longer works. Some critics have complained that some of his novels (such as *Burning Daylight*, for example) aren't novels at all, however simply strings of quick testimonies hung collectively via way of means of the merest contrivance.

London's novels traditionally incorporate as a minimum certainly considered one among 3 unique settings: the Canadian northland, wherein he started his literary apprenticeship; the primitive South Seas and Hawaii, wherein his profession started anew following a quick decline; and the California desert—in particular the Sonoma Valley—wherein London retreated over the past years of his lifestyles.

Each novel additionally usually incorporates a philosophical recognition. Popular on the time have been Charles Darwin's concept of evolution, as interpreted through Herbert Spencer; Friedrich Nietzsche's model of the superman, and, a great deal later, the brand new psychology of Sigmund Freud and Carl Jung, in addition to Karl Marx's theories of a brand new social order. All fired London's creativeness and supplied gas for his characters and plots, and their presence—especially London's model of the Darwinian “survival of the fittest” motif—lends credence to London's declare for club withinside the naturalistic faculty of fiction.

London turned into at the peak of his powers whilst he wrote *The Call of the Wild*. He changed into handling the type of concern matter, subject, and putting with which he turned into maximum comfortable. Written with energy and intensity, the unconventional became meant firstly best as a associate tale to “Batard,” an in advance brief tale. The tale literally “were given farfar from him,” as he defined in a letter to a friend, and he turned into pressured to make bigger it to its gift length. The ee-e book turned into written quickly after his go back from the slums of London. Wanting to get away the degradation and poverty he had witnessed there, London back to the clean, frozen, lovely global of the North, wherein the conflict for survival turned into elemental, uncomplicated, and fierce. The tale is that of a canine, Buck, who's abducted from his domestic on a California ranch and brought to the Yukon, in

which he's pressured to tug closely weighted down sleds for inhumane masters. In order to live on, Buck have to adapt, falling returned on primitive instincts. With domesticity stripped from him, Buck learns the approaches of his ancestors; he learns the regulation of the club—that he might be crushed however will continue to exist. Gradually, as he completes his initiation into the primitive, Buck learns to respond. He learns the regulation of the fang: that he have to be short to apply his personal fangs, earlier than others use theirs on him. By adapting to his new surroundings, Buck survives, learns the instincts of his forebears, and finally, hears the real name of the wild.

The Sea-Wolf drew on London's younger adventures withinside the sealing grounds off Japan. The novel issues the survival of upper-elegance Humphrey Van Weyden, a person who unearths himself, thru manner past his control, aboard The Ghost, a sealing schooner on its manner to Japan. Van Weyden quickly reveals that the captain of the schooner, Wolf Larsen, has created a hell-ship, full of brutality and sordidness, in which even the ship's sensible purpose—to seek seals—is misplaced withinside the distress of mere survival. Van Weyden survives this surroundings because, like Buck, he's capable of adapt to it, mastering new codes of survival, drawing upon unknown instincts, and the use of to fine benefit all of the advantages of his upbringing and status: intelligence, optimism, and a ability to like. Van Weyden's increase is the point of interest of the radical.

If The Call of the Wild is a unique approximately a canine who reacquaints himself together along with his ancestral instincts and learns survival through adaptation, White Fang is each its sequel and reverse. White Fang is the tale of a wolfdog introduced from the Alaskan desolate tract to California civilization. Just as

Buck used his civilized intelligence to live on, so White Fang makes use of his primitive power and persistence to live to tell the tale in a brand new surroundings—the arena of civilized humanity. Environment is London’s number one awareness on this novel, as he lines the modifications withinside the animal’s conduct because it movements first from the wolf percent to an American Indian village, then to the white settler, and, finally, to the Santa Clara Valley in California. White Fang is tamed through love, and he correctly makes the transition from savage wolf to loving residence pet. Although the ee-e book does now no longer have the energy of The Call of the Wild, it does display White Fang’s conflict with nature as represented with the aid of using Native Americans, dogs, white men, and finally, after important accidents suffered whilst protecting his new benevolent master, loss of life itself.

Jack London is the famous writer in the world. So, his works are attractive and written according to unusual way. When reading London’s biographies and books, something deep within me, a hunger for something more, is greatly stirred – I just want to get out and explore! Jack described this stirring in himself as a voice at the back of his consciousness –“a curiosity, desire to know, an unrest and a seeking for things wonderful that I seemed somehow to have glimpsed or guessed.” By harkening to this call, Jack had some pretty amazing adventures and was able to commit with superhuman discipline to self-education and honing his craft as a writer. But even he himself said the voice came in a whisper to him, and I think oftentimes we have a hard time hearing it – and answering it — in our own lives.

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